

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Numerical solution of a boundary value problem for a singularly perturbed equation by preliminary integration method

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to develop a discrete variant of the preliminary integration method for solving boundary value problems of singularly perturbed differential equations. In this approach, the derivatives and the solution are expanded into finite series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind. Substitution into the governing equation and matching of coefficients lead to a reduced algebraic system, which is integrated using a discrete formula, with the boundary conditions incorporated in series form. The resulting algebraic system is solved to obtain an approximate solution. The numerical results presented in tables and figures demonstrate the high accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords: Chebyshev polynomials, algebraic system, high accuracy, derivative.

In reference [2], a numerical solution of a singularly perturbed two-point boundary value problem on the interval $(0, 1)$ was obtained using the Liouville–Green transformation. In the present work, we consider the solution of this problem by applying a discrete variant of the preliminary integration method based on Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind.

It is required to find an approximate solution of the following differential equation using Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind:

$$4\varepsilon \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} - 2 \frac{dy}{dx} = 0, \quad x \in (-1, +1), \quad (1)$$

under the boundary conditions:

$$y(-1) = 1, \quad y(+1) = 0 \quad (2)$$

here ε – small parameter.

The exact solution of problem (??)-(??) has the following form [3]:

$$y(x) = \frac{e^{\frac{x-1}{2\varepsilon}} - 1}{e^{-\frac{1}{\varepsilon}} - 1} \quad (3)$$

For the numerical solution of the posed problem, we apply a discrete variant of the preliminary integration method. The main idea of this method is as follows. The highest derivative and the right-hand side of equation (1) are represented as finite series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind with unknown coefficients. Before

solving the differential problem (1)-(2), the series representing the approximate solution is preliminarily “integrated” twice using a discrete formula designed to reduce the order of the derivative.

The main advantage of this approach is that, during the integration of a finite Chebyshev series, the smoothness of the approximating polynomials increases. For example, a zeroth-order polynomial is transformed into a second-order polynomial, and so on. This, in turn, positively affects the accuracy of computations. The boundary conditions of the problem are exactly satisfied by appropriately choosing the equations for the unknown coefficients. Thus, the discrete variant of the preliminary integration method allows one to obtain an approximate solution of the problem with sufficiently high accuracy for moderate values of the small parameter.

At the collocation points of the Chebyshev polynomials, the trial function (the exact solution) of the posed problem is compared with the approximate solution obtained using the discrete variant of the preliminary integration method. We now present the algorithm of the proposed method. The second derivative is represented in the form of the following series:

$$\frac{d^2 y_a}{dx^2} = \sum_{i=0}^N 'a_i^{(2x)} T_i(x), \quad (4)$$

where u_a denotes the approximate solution of the problem $u_a = u_{\text{approximate}}$, $T_i(y)$ - is the Chebyshev polynomial i - of order, and the prime over the summation indicates that a_i the coefficients of the series are taken with a $\frac{1}{2}$ factor when $i = 0$ - are the unknown expansion coefficients [1,4].

The series (4) representing the approximate solution is integrated twice, and all lower-order derivatives, as well as the approximate solution of the problem, are obtained in the form of finite series of Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind:

$$\frac{dy_a}{dx} = \sum_{i=0}^N 'a_i^{(x)} T_i(x), \quad y_a(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N 'a_i T_i(x). \quad (5)$$

Next, by substituting series (4) and the necessary series from (5) into the differential equation (1), we obtain

$$4\epsilon \sum_{i=0}^N 'a_i^{(2x)} T_i(x) + 2 \sum_{i=0}^N 'a_i^{(x)} T_i(x) = 0$$

Then, by equating the coefficients of like powers of the polynomials, we obtain an algebraic system of the following form:

$$4\epsilon a_i^{(2x)} + 2a_i^{(x)} = 0, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, N. \quad (6)$$

For Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, the following discrete formula of preliminary integration is available, which reduces the order of derivatives in series (6):

$$a_i^{((k-1)x)} = \frac{a_{i-1}^{(kx)} - a_{i+1}^{(kx)}}{2i} \quad (7)$$

Equation (6) is integrated twice using formula (??):

a) First integration

$$4\varepsilon a_i^{(y)} + 2a_i = 0;$$

b) After the second integration, we obtain the main algebraic equation with respect to the unknown coefficients a_i :

$$4\varepsilon a_i + \frac{a_{i-1} - a_{i+1}}{i} = 0, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (8)$$

The series for the approximate solution in (5) contains $(N + 1)$ unknown coefficients a_i , ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$) the main algebraic system consists of $(N - 1)$ equations, the remaining two equations are determined from the boundary conditions (2), expressed in terms of finite series of Chebyshev polynomials. Taking into account the following properties of Chebyshev polynomials $T_i(\pm 1) = (\pm 1)^i$, the boundary conditions (2) are written in the form [3]:

$$\begin{cases} u(-1) = \frac{1}{2}a_0 - a_1 + a_2 - a_3 + \dots + a_N = 1, \\ u(+1) = \frac{1}{2}a_0 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 \dots + a_N = 0. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

First, by adding and then subtracting the equations from system (9), we obtain

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}a_0 + a_2 + a_4 + \dots + a_N = \frac{1}{2}, \\ a_1 + a_3 + a_5 + \dots + a_{N-1} = -\frac{1}{2}. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The main algebraic equations (8), together with the boundary conditions (10), form a system $(N + 1)$ of linear algebraic equations for determining $(N + 1)$ the unknowns a_i , ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$). This algebraic system has the following form:

$$\begin{cases} -a_{i-1} + 4\varepsilon i a_i + a_{i+1} = 0, \\ \frac{1}{2}a_0 + a_2 + a_4 + \dots + a_N = \frac{1}{2}, \\ a_1 + a_3 + a_5 + \dots + a_{N-1} = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad i = \overline{2, \dots, N}. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

It is convenient to represent system (11) in matrix form

$$Aa = b \quad (12)$$

where A – is a square matrix of order $M \times M$, with $M = (N + 1)$ consisting of the coefficients of system (12), $a^T = (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_N)$ is the vector of unknowns, and b – is the right-hand side of system (12). By solving system (11), the coefficients are determined; then, using formulas (3), the values of the exact solution are calculated, and using formula (5), the values of the approximate solution at the collocation points of the Chebyshev polynomials $y_l = \cos \frac{\pi l}{N}$, $l = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$ are obtained.

The differential problem (1)-(2) was solved using the discrete preliminary integration method for values of the small parameter $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$ and when the number of approximating polynomials is $N = 10, 20$. Table 1 presents the computational results for the given value of the small parameter $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$. Table 1 also shows a comparison of the exact and approximate solutions at the collocation points of the Chebyshev polynomials for $N = 10$.

The results of the comparison between the exact and approximate solutions for $N = 20$ and the same value of the small parameter $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$ are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions

ε	N	l	$u_e(y_l)$ - exact solution	$u_a(y_l)$ - approximate solution	$ u_e - u_a $ - error
10^{-2}	10	1	1.0	1.136	0.136
		3	1.0	1.171	0.171
		5	1.0	1.175	0.175
		7	0.999999999	1.170374337	0.1703743377
		9	0.9134622189	1.030226917	0.1167646985

Fig 1. Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions for $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$ and $N = 10$.

As the number of approximating polynomials increases, the absolute error between the exact and approximate solutions decreases.

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Table 2. Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions

ε	N	l	$u_e(y_l)$ - exact solution	$u_a(y_l)$ - approximate solution	$ u_e - u_a $ - error
10^{-2}	20	5	1.0	1.0032	0.0032
		10	1.0	0.994	0.006
		15	1.0	1.003	0.003

Fig 2. Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions for $\varepsilon = 10^{-2}$ and $N = 20$.

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